

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Country Dossier Morocco

WP4: Return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions and the role of the EU

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AMI	Association Migration Internationale
AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
EU	European Union
EUTF	EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GCP	Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration
IOM	International Organization for Migration
HDI	Human Development Index
MADAR	Maghreb Action on Displacement and Rights
NATLP/ANAPEC	National Agency for the Promotion of Employment and Skills
NCHR	National Council of Human Rights
NR	Nigerian returnees
OVTLP/OFPPT	Office for Vocational Training and Labor Promotion
SNIS	National Strategy for Immigration and Asylum
UNDP	United Nations Development Program
UNFPA	United Nations Population Fund
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

SUMMARY

The AMI team focused on Work Package 4 (WP4) which pertains to the case of return migration between Morocco and Nigeria. We aimed to shed additional light on the unique circumstances of these two countries that influence migration dynamics in both regions.

In addressing the main questions posed by WP4, we examined issues such as: What characterizes the governance of return migration between Morocco and Nigeria? What are the driving forces behind this governance? And how does the European Union's external migration policy shape the modalities of this governance?

To provide comprehensive answers, we first gathered quantitative and qualitative data to assess the scale of return migration from Morocco to Nigeria. We also examined the political and operational frameworks facilitating and regulating these movements.

As part of this effort, we analyzed the primary economic and socio-demographic characteristics of both Morocco and Nigeria. Additionally, we reviewed Morocco's migration policy since 2013, including the actions and strategies implemented in recent years. Our data collection encompassed all available sources to support our analysis and respond effectively to the questions raised in WP4.

From our research, we arrived at two key conclusions—one concerning Morocco and the other Nigeria.

Regarding Morocco, despite its significant legal and organizational framework, the country does not appear to prioritize the return of migrants to their countries of origin. Instead, these returns seem to be managed indirectly through the International Organization for Migration (IOM).

As for Nigerian migrants in Morocco, their numbers are relatively small compared to the total foreign migrant population in the country. Furthermore, the annual number of returnees is negligible.

Our main observations include the following:

In 2024, Nigerians accounted for 3.4% of all migrants residing in Morocco, approximately 5,000 individuals out of a total of 148,152.

In 2023, Nigerian returnees represented only 6.6% of all returnees from Morocco—134 out of 2,007 individuals. This means that just 2.6% of Nigerians living in Morocco returned home voluntarily (134 out of approximately 5,000).

These findings suggest that the return of Nigerian migrants from Morocco to Nigeria is not a critical issue for either Moroccan or Nigerian authorities.

This limited significance may explain why no formal readmission agreement exists between Morocco and Nigeria. Instead, the bilateral relationship appears to focus on other priorities, such as the status of the former Spanish Sahara (a matter of interest to Morocco) and the implementation of the Atlantic Gas Pipeline project, which is strategically important to both countries. The pipeline project which was signed in 2016 holds significant energy and diplomatic value for Morocco, particularly in terms of its relations with other West African nations.

GAPs PROJECT

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centering the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- analyze enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations, and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyze governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs' fieldwork has been conducted in 14 countries: Jordan, Lebanon, Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

This country dossier has been compiled in the context of the GAPs Work Package on ‘Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions and the Role of the EU.’

Since the vast majority of migrants and refugees move and reside in and among countries in the immediate region of their origin countries, return migration will also predominantly take place within the region of countries in crisis. Yet, scholarly concerns have overwhelmingly focused on the minority of migrants who traveled further afield, in particular to the European Union, and returned from there to their regions of origin. Relatively little attention has been given to the return policies of neighboring receiving states in the Global South.

Disregarding this regional dimension puts a Eurocentric bias on the study of return migration governance. Regional return governance, moreover, both shapes and is shaped by the externalization and return migration policies of the EU. On the one hand, the EU’s deterrence and externalization ‘partnerships’ fundamentally affect return diplomacies, infrastructures, and trajectories in its neighboring regions. On the other hand, the governance of regional returns has repercussions for the migration dynamics the EU seeks to control, for its engagement with ‘third countries,’ and for the international norms it claims to uphold.

To address this knowledge gap, therefore, this Work Package aims to better understand the intersections between (i) return migration governance within the African and Middle Eastern regions and (ii) the role of the European Union and its external migration policy. To this end, it asks three core research questions: (i) What characterizes return migration governance within African and Middle Eastern regions? Specifically: how are these modalities shaped by the EU’s external migration policy?; (ii) What are the driving forces behind these types of return migration governance? Specifically: how are these drivers affected by the EU’s external

migration policy?; and (iii) What are the effects of these drivers and modalities of regional migration governance, for both people and policy? Specifically: what are the implications of specific regional return migration governance for the EU's external migration policy? The Work Package answers these questions for eight 'host countries' (Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Türkiye, Iran, Morocco, Tunisia, Libya) focused on three 'origin countries' (Syria, Afghanistan, Nigeria).

Research in this Work Package is carried out in an embedded-multiple case study design, in which cases are selected for diversity (encompassing variation in return types) and representativeness (including main host countries in return systems that are salient to Europe, i.e., Africa, the broader Middle East). Data are generated through document analysis (a minimum of 20 documents – including academic papers, expert reports, and media coverage – have been analyzed in-depth per country dossier) and 10 (semi-structured, in-depth) expert interviews (with state authorities, international organizations, and civil society actors) have been conducted. Data was coded iteratively. First deductively, through a common codebook based on a shared conceptual framework developed to answer the three core questions listed above. Particular attention here is paid to modalities (legal, policy, and operational infrastructures), drivers (capacity and interests of actors), and outcomes (monitoring mechanisms and expert views on the sustainability of returns). Second, data was coded inductively, highlighting emerging themes that were not included in the codebook but that nevertheless surfaced as contextually relevant. Research has been subject to ethical review of the host institutions of the individual researchers conducting the country-specific research. The core concern here has been to ensure (oral) informed consent for interviews based on the full anonymity of interlocutors. Document and interview analysis have been synthesized through two workshops dedicated to these specific research phases.

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The issue of the return of migrants from Sub-Saharan countries to their countries of origin from Morocco is a very sensitive subject, both on a human and political level. It puts Morocco in the position of a protector of Europe's external borders, even though it is not a European country and the migrants who are on its territory are not seeking to settle there. Morocco is thus an obstacle to their dreams of going elsewhere. In this way, the topic of respecting the rights of migrants - in their desire to move and/or settle where they want/can - was an important part of our discussions with the officials we met as well as with the migrants themselves or representatives of their associations.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This country dossier was compiled as part of the Horizon Europe GAPs project on “Decentralizing the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond.” Specifically, it contributes to the project’s Work Package on “Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions and the Role of the EU.”

While the majority of migrants and refugees move and reside within countries near their regions of origin, return migration similarly tends to occur within these same crisis-affected areas. However, academic attention has disproportionately focused on the minority of migrants who traveled farther afield, particularly those who have gone to the European Union, and subsequently returned to their regions of origin. In contrast, relatively little attention has been given to the return policies of neighboring receiving states in the Global South.

Examining this regional dimension helps address the Eurocentric bias in the study of return migration governance. At the same time, it is essential to consider the European dimension when analyzing return governance within the African and Middle Eastern regions. This is because the European Union’s externalization and return migration policies both influence and are influenced by return dynamics in these areas.

On the one hand, the EU’s deterrence strategies and externalization “partnerships” have a profound impact on return diplomacy, infrastructure, and migration trajectories in neighboring regions.

On the other hand, the governance of regional returns has significant implications for migration dynamics that the EU seeks to control, its engagement with “third countries,” and the international norms it claims to uphold.

To address this knowledge gap, the Work Package seeks to better understand the intersections between:

- Return migration governance within the African and Middle Eastern regions, and
- The role of the European Union and its external migration policies.
- To achieve this, it focuses on three core research questions:
- What characterizes return migration governance within the African and Middle Eastern regions? Specifically, how does the EU’s external migration policy shape these countries’ internal policies?
- What are the driving forces behind these types of return migration governance? Specifically, how are these drivers influenced by the EU’s external migration policy?
- What are the effects of these governance drivers and modalities, both on people and policy? Specifically, what are the implications of specific regional return migration governance for the EU’s external migration policy?

This Work Package addresses these questions across eight “host countries” (Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Türkiye, Iran, Morocco, Tunisia, and Libya) while focusing on three key “origin countries” (Syria, Afghanistan, and Nigeria).

2. METHODS

Research in this Work Package is carried out in an embedded-multiple case study design, in which cases are selected for diversity (encompassing variation in return types) and representativeness (including main host countries in return systems that are salient to Europe, i.e., Africa, the broader Middle East). Data are generated through document analysis – including academic papers, expert reports, and media coverage – and interviews (semi-

structured, in-depth key expert interviews with state authorities, international organizations, and civil society actors). Data is coded iteratively, in two rounds: First deductively, through a common codebook based on a shared conceptual framework developed to answer the three core questions listed above. Particular attention here is paid to modalities (legal, policy, and operational infrastructures), drivers (capacity and interests of actors), and outcomes (monitoring mechanisms and expert views on the sustainability of returns). Second inductively, highlighting emerging themes not included in the codebook that are nevertheless deemed contextually relevant. Research has been subject to ethical review of the host institutions of the individual researchers conducting the country-specific research. The core concern here has been to ensure (oral) informed consent for interviews based on the full anonymity of interlocutors. Document and interview analysis have been synthesized throughout the Work Package using two workshops dedicated to these specific research phases.

3. MOROCCO GLOBAL PROFILE

As a key component of the GAPS project, Morocco plays a central role in the migration dynamics of Northern Africa. Its strategic position along key migration routes to Europe underpins its importance in shaping governance and cooperation models for return migration.

This role is particularly significant as return migration becomes an increasingly critical aspect of European migration policy, often highlighted by European Commission leadership¹.

Morocco is the westernmost nation amongst the North African countries known as the Maghreb, meaning "the West." It boasts Atlantic and Mediterranean coastlines stretching nearly 3,500 kilometers, from its northeastern border with Algeria to its southwestern border with Mauritania. Morocco's only direct neighbors to the east and southeast are these two countries.

The country covers a total surface area of 710,850 square kilometers. According to the most recent general census conducted in September 2024, Morocco's population has reached 36.828 million². Product

Its Gross Domestic (GDP) was valued at 141.11 billion USD in 2023, based on official data from the World Bank³. This equates to approximately \$3,800 per capita (around €3,650), which represents roughly 10% of the average GDP per capita in Europe⁴.

Strategically positioned along two primary routes of irregular migration to Europe from Northwest Africa, Morocco serves as a critical transit point for migrants. The Western

¹ European Commission. 10-Point Plan for Lampedusa
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/fr/IP_23_4503

& "The European Council calls for determined action at all levels to facilitate, increase, and speed up returns from the European Union, using all relevant EU policies, instruments, and tools, including diplomacy, development, trade, and visas. It invites the Commission to submit a new legislative proposal, as a matter of urgency". European Council. Brussels, 17 October 2024. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/2pebccz2/20241017-euco-conclusions-en.pdf>

² High Planning Commission, Rabat, Morocco. Result of the general population and housing census. Rabat, October 2024. <https://www.hcp.ma>

³ Morocco GDP. World Bank. <https://tradingeconomics.com/morocco/gdp>

⁴ WorldData.info. Indicators of economy in Morocco.
<https://www.worlddata.info/africa/morocco/economy.php#:~:text=Worldwide%20gross%20domestic%20product%20in,in%202023%20was%20around%206.09%25>.

Mediterranean route links Morocco with the Spanish mainland, separated by just 14 kilometers across the Strait of Gibraltar, as well as the two occupied Moroccan enclaves of Ceuta and Melilla. Meanwhile, the Western African Atlantic route connects the coasts of Senegal and Mauritania to the Canary Islands. This geographical significance necessitates reinforced border control measures, resulting in frequent arrests and pushbacks by Moroccan authorities.

As of September 1, 2024, an estimated 148,152 foreigners were residing in Morocco⁵. Compared to the previous census conducted in 2014, this represents an increase of 61,946 people over a decade, translating to an average annual growth rate of 5.6%. However, these figures do not differentiate between migrants based on the nature of their administrative status in Morocco.

Although the number of foreigners residing in Morocco represents only 0.4% of its total population, the country faces significant challenges in managing migration flows. These challenges include integrating regular migrants, combating human trafficking, and facilitating the return of migrants to their countries of origin. Moreover, Morocco is a vital partner for the European Union in migration management, particularly in the realm of border control. As such, cooperation between the EU and Morocco is crucial for addressing shared migration challenges and fostering regional development.

Despite adopting progressive migration policies, such as the “New Immigration Policy” introduced in 2013 and the National Strategy for Immigration and Asylum (NSIA), Morocco continues to grapple with internal migration issues. These include protecting migrants' rights and integrating them into Moroccan society. Bridging these objectives and developing more effective approaches to return migration requires extensive research and collaboration. Such collaboration should involve Moroccan authorities, civil society, international organizations, and development partners to formulate policies and programs that address migrants' needs and advocate for dignified and safe return migration.

It is worth noting that the solemn Declaration signed in Rabat on October 28, 2024, by the King of Morocco and the French President explicitly addresses these challenges. The Declaration states:

”The two Heads of State welcome the ambitious cooperation that they have established and strengthened in matters of migration and call for the construction of a global agenda in this area, including both the facilitation of legal mobility, the fight against irregular immigration, and cooperation in terms of readmission and prevention of departures, as well as the strengthening of coordination between countries of origin, transit, and destination, based on the principle of shared responsibility”⁶.

⁵Idem.

⁶ Declaration relating to the “Reinforced Exceptional Partnership” between the Kingdom of Morocco and the French Republic. Rabat, October 28, 2024.
<https://medias24.com/2024/10/28/le-roi-et-le-pt-macron-signent-une-declaration-sur-le-partenariat-dexception-renforce-entre-le-maroc-et-la-france/>

4. RETURN MIGRATION, A MOROCCAN NIGERIAN ISSUE?

4.1. NIGERIA – MIGRATION CONTEXT

4.1.1. NIGERIAN POPULATION

Nigeria⁷ is a political, economic, and demographic powerhouse on the African continent, frequently referred to as a "giant of Africa." This characterization is particularly fitting from a demographic perspective, as Nigeria is, and will remain, the most populous country in Africa. In 2024, its population was estimated to be between 230 and 235 million people.

However, the imprecision surrounding Nigeria's population figures raises questions about the reliability of the data. For 2024, estimates of Nigeria's population range from 229 million to 234 million, a discrepancy of nearly 2.5% of the total population. This variation highlights potential deficiencies in the country's statistical systems, leading to challenges in accurately analysing demographic data.

Different sources provide varying estimates of Nigeria's population:

- United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA): The Nigerian population in 2024 is estimated at 229.2 million⁸.
- According to Countrymeters: As of January 1, 2024, Nigeria's population was estimated at 226,166,443, with a projected increase of 6,031,859 during the year, reaching approximately 232,198,302 by early 2025⁹.
- According to Worldometer: By November 2024, Nigeria's population was reported at 234,493,750¹⁰.

Despite these discrepancies, all forecasts agree on a significant population increase in Nigeria throughout the 21st century. According to the United Nations, Nigeria's population is expected to surpass that of the United States by 2050, making it the third most populous country in the

⁷ Nigeria is located on the Central Western coast of Africa;

Area: 923,773 km²;

Administrative divisions: 36 Federal states;

Capital: Abuja. Main city: Lagos (25 million inhabitants). The 3rd largest city in the world, and the first in Africa.

Density: 230.44 inhabitants / km²;

Population: 216 million inhabitants (UNFPA), 410 million in 2050 (World Population Prospects, UN).

Most populous country in Africa, and the 7th in the world;

Rate of natural increase: 2.5% (UNFPA, 2023);

Fertility index: 5.08 children per woman (UNFPA, 2023);

Life expectancy at birth: 56 years (UNFPA, 2023).

Source: Ministry of Europe and Foreign Affairs. <https://www.diplomatie.gouv.fr/fr/dossiers-pays/nigeria/presentation-du-nigeria/>

⁸UNFPA - World Population Dashboard-Nigeria. <https://www.unfpa.org/data/world-population/NG>

⁹ Nigeria population. https://countrymeters.info/en/Nigeria#population_2024

¹⁰Worldometer. Nigeria population: <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/nigeria-population/#:~:text=The%20current%20population%20of%20Nigeria,latest%20United%20Nations%20data1.>

world¹¹. According to the World Counts¹², such a population is expected to reach 401 million in 2050 and 733 million in 2100.

4.1.2. NIGERIAN MIGRANTS

The number of Nigerians living outside their country is subject to significant discrepancies, with estimates ranging from just over 1 million to as high as 20 million, depending on the source.

- According to Prof. Aderanti Adepoju, in 2019, approximately 1.44 million Nigerian migrants were recorded in destination countries, primarily in Sub-Saharan Africa, Europe, and North America, with a smaller proportion in other regions¹³.
- In contrast, the International Organization for Migration (IOM) estimates the Nigerian diaspora at about 17 million in 2024, asserting that this community is one of the largest globally, making Nigeria the African country with the most extensive diaspora presence¹⁴.

Such imprecision in critical migration data complicates efforts to address migration challenges in the country and warrants cautious interpretation of available figures.

4.1.3. NIGERIAN ECONOMY

However, certain economic and social data are confirmed whatever the source one can refer to. These data say two important things relative to the subject of our work project. The first is that Nigeria represents, in all cases, a major country of emigration. The second lies in the observation that this same country is not able, in the economic and social conditions in which it finds itself today, to accommodate its migrants when they return to its territory.

The GDP per capita of Nigeria in 2023 was \$1,705, \$528 less than in 2022, when it was \$2,233. To have an exact view on the evolution of the GDP per capita, it is interesting to look back a few years and compare these data with those of 2013 when the Nigerian GDP per capita was \$2,947.

Based on this measure, Nigeria ranks 161st globally in countries with published GDP per capita figures, underscoring the widespread poverty affecting its population¹⁵.

Concurrently, Nigeria also has the seventh-lowest Human Development Index (HDI) worldwide. In 2023, the poverty rate reached 38.9%, with approximately 87 million Nigerians living below the poverty line – the second poorest population in the world after India¹⁶.

¹¹United Nations.

https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/pdf/events/other/10/World_Population_Projections_Press_Release.pdf

¹²<https://www.theworldcounts.com/populations/countries/nigeria>

¹³Aderanti Adepoju (ed.). 2020. “Africa Migration Report: Challenging the Narrative.” International Organization for Migration (IOM) and African Union Commission (AUC).

<https://reliefweb.int/report/world/africa-migration-report-challenging-narrative>

¹⁴ Business Insider Africa. [https://africa.businessinsider.com/local/lifestyle/foreign-countries-with-the-largest-nigerian-population/wkloz2g#:~:text=amid%20corruption%20allegations-.Data%20from%20the%20International%20Organisation%20for%20Migration%20\(IOM\)%20oputs%20the,with%20the%20biggest%20diaspora%20presence.](https://africa.businessinsider.com/local/lifestyle/foreign-countries-with-the-largest-nigerian-population/wkloz2g#:~:text=amid%20corruption%20allegations-.Data%20from%20the%20International%20Organisation%20for%20Migration%20(IOM)%20oputs%20the,with%20the%20biggest%20diaspora%20presence.) August 25, 2024

¹⁵ Countryeconomy.com <https://countryeconomy.com/gdp/nigeria>

¹⁶ World Bank Group. The World Bank in Nigeria. October 14, 2024. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/nigeria/overview>

Multidimensional poverty affected 63% of the population, while income poverty impacted 40%¹⁷. Despite a relatively low Gini coefficient of 0.35, indicating lower income inequality compared to other middle-income countries, the overall poverty levels remain alarmingly high¹⁸.

4.1.4. NIGERIAN LABOUR MARKET

Although Nigeria boasts the largest economy in Africa and is one of the continent's leading oil producers, its labour market struggles to provide sufficient employment opportunities. Approximately 3.5 million Nigerians enter the job market annually, but weak job creation leaves many unemployed or underemployed.

Nigeria is on track to becoming the third most populous country in the world. With its rapidly growing working-age population, It's projected to have an additional 100 million individuals under the age of 35 by 2040. Between 2010 and 2018, 25 million Nigerians entered the workforce, yet the unemployment rate rose sharply from 9.7% to 23.1% during the same period¹⁹.

This scarcity of opportunities drives many young Nigerians to seek employment abroad, contributing to the country's high emigration rates.

4.2. DRIVERS OF MIGRATION FROM NIGERIA

Within this global background, "Nigeria continues to experience high internal and external migration due to the size of its population, economic crisis, unemployment, insurgency, and porous borders. The combination of enduring high-intensity terrorist attacks, kidnapping, routine violence, physical insecurity, unfulfilled economic potential, and a huge population of youths with frustrated ambitions has led to massive outflows from several Nigerian states, including Lagos, Edo, and Delta states"²⁰. To all this, it is necessary to add the effects of climate change, which act on the population of this country like everything that is happening on the rest of the African continent²¹.

¹⁷ According to the UNDP, "For Nigeria, the HDI has shown a 22% increase in 19 years but remains low at 0.548, categorizing the country as having low human development. The report emphasizes Nigeria's significant loss in HDI due to inequality, estimated at 32.7%. Gender disparities persist, with a notable gap between male and female HDI values and a Gender Inequality Index (GII) ranking placing Nigeria poorly. Furthermore, Nigeria's Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) indicates that 33% were multidimensionally poor in 2021". <https://www.undp.org/nigeria/news/valuable-insights-and-findings-2023/2024-human-development-report-and-its-correlation-nigerias-human-development-index>

¹⁸<https://www.afdb.org/en/countries-west-africa-nigeria/nigeria-economic-outlook>

¹⁹Samik Adhikari, Michael Clemens, Helen Dempster, andNkechi Linda Ekeator"Expanding Legal Migration Pathways from Nigeria to Europe: From Brain Drain to Brain Gain". Samik Adhikari, Michael Clemens, Helen Dempster, and Nkechi Linda Ekeator. World Bank, Center of Global Development & KWPF <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/099820506212215126/pdf/P1709640189d3702408c17026c70078e415.pdf> .

²⁰ Solomon Obanlais. "Nigerian Demography And Challenges Of Irregular Migration". <https://www.themigrationnews.com/news/nigerian-demography-and-challenges-of-irregular-migration/>

²¹ Climate Change And Migration In Africa "While Africa contributes the least to climate change (Africa is responsible for less than 4% of the global greenhouse gas emissions), it is being hit the hardest by its effect. Of the estimated 140 million climate-related migrants in 2050, more than half the stock (more than 86 Million people) will be from Africa".

In this sense, economic hardship is a primary driver of irregular migration from Nigeria. High unemployment rates, especially among the youth, and the lack of viable economic opportunities compel many Nigerians to seek better prospects abroad²². Also, political instability and insecurity are critical push factors for migration in this country, probably more than many other areas in Africa. Nigeria has faced numerous internal conflicts, including the Boko Haram insurgency in the northeast and herdsmen-farmer clashes across various regions leading to more than 1 million internally displaced²³. Thus, the Africa Migration Report notes that political and security crises in Nigeria have exacerbated the conditions that lead to illegal migration, as many people flee violence and persecution²⁴.

Environmental degradation and climate change also play a great role in driving migration. Nigeria is one of the countries most vulnerable to climate change's impact, characterized by unpredictable and erratic rainfall, droughts, and desertification. In addition, in regions like the Niger Delta, oil pollution has devastated local livelihoods, particularly those dependent on fishing and agriculture. This environmental degradation forces people to migrate²⁵, at least in search of a less degraded living environment.

Similarly, the trend of Nigerian migration through irregular routes to North Africa is closely linked to the limited availability of legal migration channels and the appeal of perceived opportunities in Europe²⁶. This pattern reflects a broader trend observed across various regions, where restrictive immigration policies drive migrants towards clandestine routes in pursuit of better prospects.

5. MOROCCO TRANSIT MIGRATION CONTEXT: DATA, THE CONSTITUTIONAL AND POLITICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE NEW MOROCCAN MIGRATION POLICY

The Mediterranean Sea has served as a crucial trade and migration route for centuries, shaping the geopolitical landscape of the regions it borders. Morocco, strategically located at the crossroads of Africa and Europe, has become a significant transit country for migrants from sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria²⁷. The Sahel (the Sahara Desert) led them to the Moroccan coasts where they embarked on boats towards Spain's mainland, the Canary Islands, or by land through the enclave Ceuta and Melilla. By the beginning of the actual century,

[https://sihma.org.za/online-resources/climate-change-and-migration-in-africa#:~:text=While%20Africa%20contributes%20the%20least,people\)%20will%20be%20from%20Africa.](https://sihma.org.za/online-resources/climate-change-and-migration-in-africa#:~:text=While%20Africa%20contributes%20the%20least,people)%20will%20be%20from%20Africa.)

²²the National Migration Profile 2019, IOM-Nigeria; p33

https://nigeria.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd11856/files/documents/2024-04/the-national-migration-profile-2019_o.pdf

²³ 1,092,196 IDPs in Nigeria according to Round 13 IDP Atlas (March 2024). IOM, Nigeria

<https://dtm.iom.int/reports/nigeria-north-central-and-north-west-round-13-idp-atlas-march-2024>

²⁴Africa Migration Report (Second edition) Connecting the threads: Linking policy, practice and the welfare of the African migrant

²⁵ The National Migration Profile 2019, IOM Nigeria; p33

https://nigeria.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd11856/files/documents/2024-04/the-national-migration-profile-2019_o.pdf

²⁶Adepoju, A., van Naessen, T. and Zoomers, A. (eds.) (2007) International Migration and National Development in sub-Saharan Africa: viewpoints and policy initiatives in the countries of origin. Afrika-Studiecentrum Series, 10. Brill Publishers, Leiden.

²⁷ National survey on forced migration in Morocco, 2021,

file:///C:/Users/delll/Downloads/La%20migration%20forc%C3%A9e%20au%20Maroc,%20r%C3%A9sultats%20de%20l'enqu%C3%AAta%20nationale%20de%202021,%20rapport%20d%C3%A9tail%20C3%A9%20(1).pdf

Morocco had witnessed an influx of irregular migrants, with a maximum of almost 23,000 (23,851) persons in 2003 (see Table 1, below).

The presence of Nigerians has been noticed in Morocco, in parallel with the presence of other migrants coming from countries south of the Sahara, since the beginning of the current century, with many using the country as both a transit and destination space. However, precise figures on Nigerian migrants in Morocco are challenging to ascertain due to the mixed nature of migration flows and the prevalence of irregular migration. But, even if IOM reported that Nigerian nationals are among the top nationalities traveling within the West and Central Africa region through the Sahel between January and March 2024²⁸, the number of Nigerians living in Morocco seems to be limited. Indeed, according to the president of the Nigerian Association-Morocco, “We should be talking within the range of 5,000 Nigerians living in Morocco. Some haven’t been documented in our registers but from what we have that includes students, non-students, and legal migrants”²⁹. The number of 5,000 people represents less than 3.4% of the total foreign population living in Morocco in September 2024³⁰.

5.1. MOROCCO: A TRANSIT COUNTRY!

Morocco became a transit country as sub-Saharan African migrants used it as a gateway to Europe, primarily due to its proximity to Spain.

But, over time, stricter European border controls made it harder for migrants to continue their journey, leading many to settle in Morocco either temporarily or permanently. This shift, from being a transit hub to a destination country, prompted Morocco to reform its migration policies, including efforts to integrate and regularize migrants. Morocco will adopt, by 2013/2014, a new migratory representing a great change, in the space of 10 years (between 2003 and 2013) from a strong predominance of security to a more social and humanitarian perspective, even if the basic law governing migration remains the one that was adopted in 2003, namely Law 02-03.

Available data show that, between the years 2000 and 2011, a little bit over 166,200 foreign migrants passed through Morocco on their way to Europe. This gives an annual average of just over 12,900 migrants. However, with a sharp drop from 2006, the number of transit migrants in 2009 represented only less than 50% of what it was in 2003 or 2005, as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: evolution of the irregular migration from Morocco, 2000-2011

Years	Moroccans	Foreigners	Total
2000	9,353	15,056	24,409
2001	13,327	13,100	26,427
2002	16,034	15,363	31,397
2003	12,493	23,851	36,344

²⁸ WEST AND CENTRAL AFRICAN ROUTES THROUGH SAHEL Coverage: January-March 2024
Publication: May 2024

²⁹<https://punchng.com/nigerians-wont-flee-morocco-over-earthquake-deaths-nam-president/>.
September 16, 2023.

³⁰ See, High Commission for Planning (HCP), “Legal Population of Morocco”, 2024 (in French).
<https://www.hcp.ma>

2004	9,353	17,252	26,605
2005	7,914	21,894	29,808
2006	7,091	9,469	16,560
2007	6,619	7,830	14,449
2008	4,651	8,735	13,386
2009	2,672	7,531	10,203
2010	ND ^o	10,223	10,223
2011	ND	12,929	12,929

Source: M. Lahlou, "Morocco's Experience of Migration as a Sending, Transit and Receiving Country". IAI -Istituto Affari Internazionali, Roma, 2015.³¹

The same downward trend in the number of migrants transiting through Morocco, on their way to Europe, is confirmed by Table 2 below, which shows Frontex data on irregular movement migrants in the Mediterranean as a whole, as well as in the Western Mediterranean route³², which is the passageway between Morocco, Algeria, and Spain.

Table 2: irregular movements of migrants on the west-Mediterranean route about all similar migrations in the Mediterranean - 2008-2023

Years	Total Migrants (all routes) 1	West-Mediterranean route 2	2/1
2008	151,135	6,500	4.3%
2010	104,120	5,000	4.8%
2012	73,160	6,400	7.75%
2013	101,800	6,800	6.68%
2014	283,175	7,840	2.75%
2015	1,822,337	7,164	0.39%
2016	374,638	10,231	2.73%
2017	184,410	23,143	12.55%
2018	149,117	56,245	37.71%
2019	141,846	23,969	16.89%
2021	202,322	18,466	9.12 %

³¹ <https://www.iai.it/en/pubblicazioni/moroccos-experience-migration-sending-transit-and-receiving-country>. ND: Not determined.

³² Designated as such by Frontex, this route leads from northwest Africa (Morocco & Algeria) to southern Spain. For migrant movements from West Africa, Frontex refers to the West African Route. The latter concerns departures from Morocco but also from Senegal or Mauritania to the Canary Islands.

2022	326.335	15 134	4,6%
2023	380.227	16 915	4,44%

Source: Compiled by M. Lahlou. From <http://frontex.europa.eu/trends-and-routes/migratory-routes-map/> 2016 and “Risk Analysis” for 2016 & 2018. March 2016 and February 2018. + Risk analysis 2020³³ & Frontex Annual Brief, 2023³⁴.

The above data (especially those in Table 2), where migrants from south of the Sahara seem to have become, in particular since 2019, a minority in the western Mediterranean due, according to us, to three reasons. The first is that these migrants – for many reasons, including the tightening of controls on maritime areas in the Strait of Gibraltar and the borders of the cities of Ceuta and Melilla and the shift of South-North African migration routes to the central Mediterranean – tend to travel via Tunisia or Libya or through the Atlantic corridors, the West African Route, first, towards the Canary Islands, especially since the health crisis of 2020/2021.

This observation appears in the data relating to recent years, as published by Frontex.

Thus, between 2018 and 2022, 113,814 irregular migrants would have passed into Spain via the West-Mediterranean Route. Of this number, there would have been only 9,110 migrants from sub-Saharan Africa, i.e. an average of less than 2,000/year³⁵.

The second reason, probably the most decisive, would be linked to the strong control of Moroccan borders by the Moroccan security forces themselves. This is notably attested by the available data relating to the arrests of irregular migrants, Moroccans, and foreigners as well, at the country's land and maritime borders.

The latter indicates, as revealed in Table 3 below, that between 2013 and 2022 there were 506,731 attempted irregular crossings through Morocco's borders, 71% of which were initiated by foreign migrants, sub-Saharan Africans for the largest share. The peak having been reached in 2018, with 880,761 attempts, of which 70,571 were the work of foreigners.

Table 3: Irregular migratory movements from and to Morocco, 2013 to 2022

Year	Interception of Moroccan candidates for irregular migration	Interception of foreign candidates for irregular migration
2013	7,359	24,880
2014	11,586	26,230
2015	7,273	28,211
2016	7,064	29,286
2017	13,261	50,961
2018	18,190	70,571
2019	17,134	56,839

³³https://frontex.europa.eu/assets/Publications/Risk_Analysis/Risk_Analysis/Annual_Risk_Analysis_2020.pdf

³⁴ https://www.frontex.europa.eu/assets/Publications/General/Annual_Brief_2023.pdf

³⁵Frontex risk analysis – 2019/2023. <https://www.frontex.europa.eu/>

2020	20,243	20,045
2021	30,612	32,509
2022	11,908	22,369

Source : Nations Unies. “Convention internationale sur la protection des droits de tous les travailleurs migrants et des membres de leur famille”. Text in French. November, 28, 2022

<file:///C:/Users/21266/Downloads/G2260090.pdf>

The third reason is often attached, especially in the official language, to the measures for the integration of migrants agreed in the framework of the migration policy carried out by the Moroccan authorities since the beginning of 2014. A policy that, by acknowledging the fact that Morocco has also become a host country (to a certain extent), has changed its approach to managing migration on its territory. This seems to be confirmed by the results of the latest census carried out by Morocco, which indicate that 148,152 foreigners were present in Morocco, in September 2024. This means an increase, in absolute figures, of 61,946 people compared to 2014 (the year of the penultimate census) and a 5.6% annual growth rate between 2014 and 2024³⁶. This does not make Morocco a major host country for foreign populations. The latter – including the distribution between people legally settled on the national territory and those who are not – represent less than 0.4% of the total Moroccan population.

5.1. MOROCCAN MIGRATION POLICY

Morocco became a transit country as sub-Saharan African migrants used it as a gateway to Europe, primarily due to its proximity to Spain. But, over time, stricter European border controls made it harder for migrants to continue their journey, leading many to settle in Morocco either temporarily or permanently. This shift, from being a transit hub to a destination country, prompted Morocco to reform its migration policies, including efforts to integrate and regularize migrants. Morocco will adopt, by 2013/2014, a new migratory approach representing a great change, in the space of 10 years (between 2003 and 2013) from a strong predominance of security to a more social and humanitarian perspective. Even if the basic law governing migration remains the one that was adopted in 2003, namely Law 02-03.

It seems to us that three reasons have led Morocco to change its migratory approach since the beginning of the 2010s:

- The first is probably because Moroccan officials thought that the significant migratory flows, from Africa, had definitively moved towards the east and center of the Mediterranean, as confirmed by the above data.
- The second, was to anticipate accusations made against its police forces, in particular by the BBC, in September 2013³⁷.
- The third is that the Moroccan government was probably preparing the return of the

³⁶ See, High Commission for Planning (HCP), “Legal Population of Morocco”, 2024 (in French). <https://www.hcp.ma>

³⁷ BBC, “Morocco accused of human rights breaches over migrants”. September 4, 2013. <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-23959892>

country to the Organization of the African Union, to better defend, among other things, its claim to the former Spanish Sahara

In reality, this would be the first reason which would have motivated the change in question here. The adoption and implementation of Morocco's "New Migration Policy" in 2013 would have been promoted in link with the changing migration flows, in light of what happened in the Mediterranean (in Tunisia, Libya, and Syria, in particular) following the Arab Spring, which led, notably, to the 2015 European/Mediterranean refugee crisis.

5.1.1. THE CONSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK OF THE NEW MIGRATION POLICY

The Migration Policy adopted by Morocco, by the end of 2013, draws much of its substance from the constitution voted by Moroccans in July 2011, as one of the consequences of the "Moroccan Arab Spring". This constitution came to translate into the Moroccan legal sphere as one of the foundations of the "Global constitutional reform" mentioned by the King of Morocco in a speech delivered in March 2011. The foundation in question consisted of 'The consolidation of the rule of law and institutions, the broadening of the scope of individual and collective freedoms and the guarantee of their exercise, as well as the strengthening of the system of Human rights in all their dimensions (including the rights of migrants), political, economic, social, cultural, environmental and development"³⁸.

In this sense, the preamble of the new Moroccan Constitution, adopted by referendum states that the Kingdom of Morocco "undertakes to adhere to the principles, rights, and obligations set in the respective charters and conventions" and "reaffirms its commitment to universally recognized human rights and its willingness to continue to work to maintain peace and security throughout the world"³⁹. In this regard, the Kingdom reaffirms its commitment to "let duly ratified international conventions prevail over domestic law...and bring the relevant provisions of its national legislation into line accordingly". The International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of their Families thus serves as a regulatory framework.

Article 16 of the Constitution stipulates that "The Kingdom of Morocco shall work to protect the legitimate rights and interests of Moroccan citizens living abroad, by international law and the laws in force in the host countries"⁴⁰. The preamble reaffirms the country's commitment to "Prohibit and combat all discrimination against any individual on the grounds of sex, colour, creed, culture, social or regional origin, language, disability or any personal circumstances".

Also, article 30 of the Constitution provides that "Foreigners shall enjoy the same fundamental freedoms granted to Moroccan citizens, by the law. Those who reside in Morocco may participate in local elections by the law, the application of International conventions or reciprocal arrangements"⁴¹.

³⁸Maroc.ma. Kingdom of Morocco. Text of the speech delivered by the King on March 9, 2011. <https://www.maroc.ma/fr/discours-royaux/texte-int%C3%A9gral-du-discours-adress%C3%A9-par-sm-le-roi-la-nation>

³⁹Moroccan Constitution, 2011. Reference document in Arabic version. English Translation © 2012 by William S. Hein & Co., Inc. https://www.constituteproject.org/constitution/Morocco_2011

⁴⁰ Idem

⁴¹ Idem

Such an article, on its own, clearly represents a basis for the NSIA which will be decided by the Moroccan government three years later⁴².

5.1.2. MOROCCAN MIGRATION POLICY

For political and many other reasons (financial, logistic, diplomatic, etc.)⁴³, Morocco did not see any interest in the last decades of the twentieth century to change its approach towards migration flows, even irregular, from the rest of Africa, which meant that the kingdom became an easy transit space for Sub-Saharan migrants bound for Europe (to which they started entering rather easily through the cities of Ceuta and Melilla). At that time, and until 2000, it probably considered that the number of irregular migrants transiting its territory (fewer than 8,000 people) was not significant⁴⁴. It may also have considered, given its bad relationships with Spain⁴⁵, that it had no reason to help this country to protect itself from irregular migrants.

However, after that period the Moroccan government began gradually to adopt another approach, closer to European aims and options, in particular for the surveillance and control of its borders – especially regarding Spain, for which it is the nearest African country. The first signaling the change in the Moroccan migration policy came towards the end of 2002, the year when Morocco and Spain entered into an open war as a result of the territorial conflict around the small Perejil Island⁴⁶(Which is situated less than 200 meters from the Moroccan Mediterranean coast). This phase seems to follow the decisions taken by the European Council during its meeting held in Seville, Spain, in June 2002⁴⁷. Most probably inspired by the Spanish Prime Minister, the European Council linked, for the first time, the relations of the EU with third countries and the migration policy pursued by these countries. At that time, Morocco – supposed then to facilitate the passage of irregular migrants through its territory – was the focus in mind⁴⁸.

In this report, we do not deal with the migration policies adopted by Morocco since the beginning of the century. This concerns very little the subject of our WP, since the question of migrant returns was not then topical. (See Annex 1).

⁴²Global Forum on Migration and Development, “Morocco's National Strategy on Immigration and Asylum”. April 28, 2015. <https://www.gfmd.org/pfp/ppd/2080>

⁴³ According to the UNDP, Morocco is ranked in 2022, 120th out of 193 countries, behind several of its regional neighbors, including Libya, Algeria, and Tunisia.

<https://www.morocoworldnews.com/2024/05/362715/is-morocco-really-doing-badly-in-human-development>

As a result of this, his financial and financial resources are limited.

In parallel, its diplomatic position among African countries was (and still is) complicated due to the ex-Spanish Sahara conflict which opposes it to Algeria since 1975.

⁴⁴ L. Barros, M. Lahlou & al., “L’immigration irrégulière subsaharienne à travers et vers le Maroc”, in Cahier des migrations internationales, No. 54F (2002), p. 88.

http://www.ilo.org/global/topics/labourmigration/WCMS_201832.

⁴⁵ Mainly because of issues of fisheries and agricultural exchanges with Europe. And also in keeping with the animosity of the Spanish government, headed at the beginning of the current century by Prime Minister Aznar (leader of the Popular Party - PP) who was openly hostile to Morocco.

⁴⁶ The island is called Laïla by the Moroccans and is situated less than 1km from Morocco’s northern coast.

⁴⁷ Seville European Council, 21 and 22 June 2002. Presidency Conclusions.

<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/20928/72638.pdf>

⁴⁸ M. Lahlou, Les migrations irrégulières entre le Maghreb et l’Union européenne : évolutions récentes, Migration Policy Centre. CARIM Research Report, 2005/03 - <https://hdl.handle.net/1814/6278>

5.1.2.1. THE NEW MOROCCAN MIGRATION POLICY

As indicated in Table 2 above, the number of irregular migrants using the western Mediterranean route, including Morocco with its two sea coasts, increased to 7,842 in 2014 from only 5,003 in 2010. However, the 2014 figure is still well below the figures reached between 2001 and 2005, even if the total number of irregular migrants who arrived in Europe in 2014 has almost tripled by comparison with 2013, increasing from 107,365 to 283,532⁴⁹. That means that the controls all along the Moroccan borders are rigorous, confirming the will of Morocco to continue to adapt its migration policy to that of Europe. This has been reinforced by the “advanced status” granted by the EU to Morocco in October 2008⁵⁰ as by the “Mobility partnership” linking Moroccans to Europeans since April 2013.

This last agreement has three main objectives. The first aims to “manage more effectively the movement of people for short periods and legal labor migration, taking into account the labor market situation of the signatory European countries”; The second is to “combat illegal immigration, networks involved in trafficking and smuggling of human beings; The third is to promote an effective return and readmission policy, while respecting fundamental rights, relevant legislation and ensuring the dignity of the persons concerned⁵¹.” But neither Moroccans nor Europeans are completely satisfied with its application. Moroccans, because they believe that the conditions for obtaining visas for the Schengen space to which they are subject are still too restrictive; the Europeans, because after 16 rounds of negotiations, they still haven't gotten from the Moroccans the “readmission agreement” they've been demanding for years⁵². According to AMI's members, and many migrant association members, this is probably because the Moroccans consider that it's one of the last cards that remains in their hands in their global negotiations with Europe (with the hope that they will not change about it). Another consideration is that it is the sort of agreement that would be very expensive for them financially and politically to implement. Both arguments are not contradictory, moreover. With this in mind, and probably as a reaction to a BBC documentary broadcast published on September 4, 2013, when Morocco was accused of “human rights breaches over migrants”⁵³, King Mohamed VI held a meeting with the Ministry of Home Affairs and some

⁴⁹ In April 2015, Frontex published figures for illegal immigration in Europe for the year 2014. According to its data, the number of illegal immigrants in the EU almost tripled in 2014 compared with the previous year, an increase of 164 percent. The first migration route remains the sea. Over 170,000 irregular migrants arrived in Italy and more than 50,000 in Greece. See Frontex, Annual Risk Analysis 2015, cit.,p.12 and 19.

⁵⁰ On 13 October 2008, Morocco became the first country in the southern Mediterranean region to be granted advanced status, marking a new phase of privileged relations. “The Advanced Status is reflected in the willingness to strengthen political dialogue, and cooperation in the economic, social, parliamentary, judicial, and security fields and different sectors, namely agriculture, transportation, energy, and environment. It also aims at the progressive integration of Morocco into the EU single market as well as at increasing legislative and regulatory convergence. Financial cooperation plays an essential support role in the success of this special relationship”. See the European Commission webpage on International Cooperation and Development: Morocco, <http://ec.europa.eu/EuropeAid/countries/Morocco.en>

⁵¹Council of the European Union, Joint declaration establishing a Mobility Partnership between the Kingdom of Morocco and the European Union and its Member States (ST 6139 2013 ADD 1 REV 3), 3 June 2013, p. 4,<http://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-6139-2013-ADD-1-REV-3/en/pdf>.

⁵² See Annex 3.

⁵³Paul Mason, “Morocco accused of human rights breaches over migrants”, in BBC News, 4 September 2013,

human rights representatives (among the National Council of Human Rights – CNDH) on 10 September 2013 to initiate a new “migration and asylum policy” for foreign residents in the kingdom, especially illegal migrants⁵⁴. This announcement was regarded as another turning point in Morocco’s human rights approach to irregular immigrants, mainly sub-Saharanans from countries like Mali, Senegal, Niger, Nigeria, Côte d’Ivoire and Guinea Conakry, but also refugees from Libya and Syria.

5.2.2.2. The New Migration Policy: A three pillars approach

By the end of 2013, and while Morocco began to experience a kind of "migratory peace" - in 2015, less than 0.40% of trans-Mediterranean migrations transiting through its territory and maritime space - the country adopted a "New Migration Policy", qualified as "more humane" and based on three pillars:

A political one consisting of the commitment of the king in person on the subject. This follows a report by the CNDH entitled "Foreigners and Human Rights in Morocco: for a radically new asylum and immigration policy";

An operational pillar that consisted of two exceptional operations to regularize migrants in an irregular situation. Thus, in 2014 and late 2016-2017, Morocco conducted two operations to regularize the administrative status of foreigners residing irregularly on national territory. These operations were based on flexible criteria and resulted in the regularization of over 50,000 migrants. The regularization of individuals with irregular residence status allowed them to enjoy their rights and integration opportunities in Moroccan society, provided under the National Immigration and Asylum Strategy.

A pillar of Public Policy consisting in the adoption, at the end of 2014, of the NSIA followed in 2015 by a "National Strategy for Moroccans Residing Abroad". More specifically, the SNIA was to lead to the adoption of laws allowing better integration of migrants and asylum seekers into social life in Morocco. In this sense, several public structures will be involved, since the authorities will proceed, among other actions, to facilitate migrants' access to the training provided by the Office for Vocational Training and Labor Promotion (OFPPT), to the training programs provided by the Centre of the National Mutual Aid (*entraide Nationale/National Solidarity*) to the job search services provided by the National Agency for the Promotion of Employment and Skills (ANAPEC).

In the same context, and at another level, a more marked fight against human traffickers will be announced to reduce networks facilitating irregular movements to and from Morocco. Thus, as an extension of the Migration Policy decided since the end of 2013, a new law will be adopted – Law 27-14, to eradicate Human trafficking including that which affects migrants (See Annex 2). This will be done in parallel with the commitment of Public Authorities to give expanded power to the headquarters of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) in Rabat to grant, in particular, the right of asylum to a larger number of asylum seekers in Morocco.

<http://www.bbc.com/news/business-23959892>.

⁵⁴ Even if official spokesmen and public media attached this initiative to a report on the issue of irregular migration published by the CNDH, some observers were to link this initiative to the BBC documentary.

5.2.2.3. The National Strategy for Immigration and Asylum (NSIA)

The Ministry in Charge of the Moroccans Living Abroad and Migration Affairs worked out, at the end of 2014, a “National Strategy on Immigration and Asylum.”. Such a strategy, adopted by a Government Council held on December 18, 2014, has as a vision to ensure a better integration of the immigrants and a better management of the migration flux within the framework of a “coherent, overall, humanistic and responsible policy”.

This Strategic vision was founded on three main objectives:

Objective 1: Facilitating the integration of legal immigrants.

This objective consists of ensuring the integration of regular migrants, making them enjoy the same rights as Moroccans (access to education, vocational training, employment, medical coverage, housing, etc..), combating discrimination, and ensuring the conditions for a dignified and fulfilled life (family reunification, political/associative participation, etc..).

Objective 2: Upgrading the regulatory framework

This objective consists of establishing a regulatory framework that takes into account Morocco's immigration and human rights guidelines, the provisions of the Constitution, and the international conventions signed.

Objective 3: Establishing an appropriate institutional framework

This objective consists of establishing the institutional and governance framework allowing better collaboration between the actors concerned by the issue of immigration and synergy in the implementation of the actions provided for in the framework of the said strategy.

These objectives seem, a priori, to be very promising, indicating a desire to meet the integration needs of migrants living on Moroccan territory. However, on the ground, certain limitations have emerged that greatly reduce its scope. The first would be linked to the observation that only regularized migrants should benefit from it. However, these only represent a part of the migrants present in Morocco (see data above), and are only regularized, when the conditions are met for this, for one year.

The second concerns the ignorance of most migrants of the existence of Law 02-03, the new migration policy and the SNIA. In this sense, the majority of migrants are not informed of the existence of texts and policies governing their presence in Morocco, as indicated in the table below.

Thus, it appears – according to a survey we led in 2022, that less than 30% of the migrants we interviewed then were informed of the content of these policies. Less than 25% were aware of the new Moroccan migration policy, more than 80% were unaware of the NSIA and only 16% were aware of Law 02-03. On all these elements, there are very few differences between men and women, as shown in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Migrants informed about Moroccan migration policies/actions

Policy/Action	All the sample	Migrant women	Migrant men
Migration laws and policies are applied today in Morocco.	29 %	35 %	26 %
Law 02-03	16 %	15 %	17 %
New Migration Policy	23 %	21 %	24 %
National Immigration and Asylum Strategy	18 %	12 %	21 %

Source: M. Lahlou & Ghali Abdelali, Field survey, Morocco, January-March 2022. In Morocco country profile. MADAR Project. www.keele.ac.uk/

In addition to various relevant international instruments that Morocco has ratified in recent years, the country was among the first signatories of the “Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration” (GCM). This Compact enumerates objectives for State action, bolstered by specific commitments that seek to address challenges related to today’s migration. Its commitments and actions can be seen as a guide for States to meet their human rights obligations when designing migration governance measures to reduce the risks and vulnerabilities migrants face at different stages of migration and to create conducive conditions that empower all migrants to become active members of society.

The Global Compact, as adopted in Marrakech in December 2018, refers to several international commitments to protect and improve the living conditions of migrants, including:

- Protecting the safety, dignity human rights, and fundamental freedoms of all migrants, regardless of their migratory status, and at all times;
- Supporting countries rescuing, receiving, and hosting large numbers of refugees and migrants;
- Integrating migrants – addressing their needs and capacities as well as those of receiving communities – in humanitarian and development assistance frameworks and planning;
- Combating xenophobia, racism, and discrimination toward all migrants;
- Developing, through a state-led process, non-binding principles and voluntary guidelines on the treatment of migrants in vulnerable situations; and
- Strengthening global governance of migration, including by bringing IOM into the UN family and through the development of a Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration.

As explained above, Morocco has gradually put in place a legislative and legal arsenal to enable it to approach the migration issue in the best possible terms. This is both to safeguard the rights of migrants and refugees and to control its borders or to strengthen its diplomatic position in the context of its relations on the subject – and others - both with EU countries

and with the rest of African countries. During the bibliographic and field work that we are carrying out as part of our project, we will see in particular to what limits the new Moroccan migratory approach has been consistent with the developments observed over the last few years and to what extent its various objectives have been effective for the targeted populations.

6. FINDINGS

6.1. DATA AND THE ROLE OF IOM

The main findings resulting from our work are, first, of all quantitative. These relate to the data we collected. These data indicate a relatively low presence of Nigerian migrants in Morocco as well as a very low number of returnees to Nigeria from Morocco. Compared, for example, to the Senegalese, Guineans, or Ivorians. For the rest, with regard to our collection of data, apart from those provided by the High Commission for Planning (which relate in particular to the general population census) it was very difficult to obtain certain detailed data or data series from the Moroccan Ministry of the Interior, which has control over the security aspect of the migration issue in Morocco.

Regarding the annual figures published by Frontex, they are not sufficiently detailed. Because 1/ they do not always reveal details by nationality regarding migrants intercepted at sea and at the borders of Europe; 2/ regarding the two migratory routes, West Mediterranean and West Africa, it is not possible to separate the intercepted migrants according to whether they come from Morocco or Algeria, for what concerns the West Mediterranean Route. While the West African Route, heading towards the Canary Islands, concerns departures from Morocco as well as from the Mauritanian or Senegalese coasts.

On the institutional level, the IOM, the source of most of the data reported in this report, has been involved for almost 20 years in supporting the return of migrants from Morocco. Before the signing of the headquarters agreement on February 22, 2005, in Geneva, ratified in June 2007 to provide IOM with representation in Morocco, the country committed, with its means, to facilitate the voluntary return of irregular migrants to their countries of origin. It was from signing a Memorandum of Understanding between Morocco and IOM on June 11, 2007, that the latter was tasked with implementing the voluntary return and reintegration program⁵⁵.

Following collaboration between the Moroccan Ministry of Interior and IOM, a second amendment to the memorandum of understanding of June 11, 2007, was signed in June 2015⁵⁶. The AVRR Program (Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration)⁵⁷ enabled

⁵⁵ Memorandum signed by IOM and the Moroccan Ministry of Interior. <https://www.maroc.ma/en/news/morocco-iom-sign-amendment-mou-illegal-immigrants-voluntary-return-reintegration-origin>

⁵⁶A second amendment of the memorandum of understanding (MoU) to implement the cooperation program between Morocco and the International Organization for Migration (IOM), related to the voluntary return and reintegration in origin countries of illegal immigrants in Morocco, was signed, on Monday, June 1, 2015, in Rabat. <https://www.maroc.ma/en/news/morocco-iom-sign-amendment-mou-illegal-immigrants-voluntary-return-reintegration-origin>

⁵⁷ IOM, What is the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration programme (AVRR)? https://morocco.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbdl936/files/documents/en_fiche_avrr_20210517_v2.pdf

thousands of distressed migrants to return to their countries of origin since 2005, who could not do so with their means.

According to the IOM–Rabat⁵⁸, since the implementation of this program in 2005, the total number of beneficiaries of voluntary return is 20,535.

The average annual number of returnees increased from 470, between 2005 and 2013, to 1,445 between 2014 and 2019, before reaching 2,417 between 2021 and 2022.

In this way, the number of returnees in 2022 represents more than 5 times the average number recorded between 2005 and 2013. This may indicate an increase in the number of irregular migrants present in Morocco as a greater effort of Moroccan authorities and the IOM, as well as an effective/on-field regional cooperation to help migrants, who want to return to their countries of origin, to do so.

The part of Nigerians on all migrants living in Morocco (in 2024) is 3.4%, that is about 5,000 persons out of 148,152.

The part of Nigerian returnees (NR) in all returnees from Morocco in 2023 represents only less than 7% (6.6%). That is, in that year, 134 out of 2007 returned home voluntarily. And the part of NR on Nigerians living in Morocco is 2.6% (134 out of about 5,000).

This indicates that the return of Nigerian migrants from Morocco to Nigeria is not a crucial matter neither for Moroccans nor for Nigerian authorities.

6.2. DRIVING FORCES OF RETURN MIGRATION GOVERNANCE FROM MOROCCO TO NIGERIA

6.2.1. INTERESTS OF RETURN MIGRATION GOVERNANCE: DOMESTIC AND EXTERNAL

Domestic Interests: Morocco's domestic interests in return migration governance are driven by the need to maintain social stability and manage its resources effectively. By participating in return migration programs, Morocco aims to reduce the number of irregular migrants within its borders, thereby alleviating pressure on its social services and infrastructure. The domestic narrative also emphasizes fairness, where the government argues that Morocco should not bear disproportionate responsibility for migrants⁵⁹ who are not its nationals but merely transited through its territory⁶⁰. This perspective is crucial in domestic

⁵⁸ The IOM leads the implementation of the AVRR program in close collaboration with the Moroccan Ministry of the Interior, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, African Cooperation, Moroccans Residing Abroad, and some countries of destination as of origin of assisted migrants, with the financial support of the EU.

⁵⁹ According to the Moroccan Minister of Foreign Affairs, "Transit countries must not be unfairly singled out. Placing the weight of this migration on these countries would be the antithesis of shared responsibility. The latter consists of balanced partnerships, which corresponds to equal treatment because Africa is not looking for aid, it is looking for partners. July 26, 2023. <https://diplomatie.ma/fr/m-nasser-bourita-prend-part-aux-travaux-de-la-conf%C3%A9rence-internationale-sur-le-d%C3%A9veloppement-et-la-migration-qui-se-tient-%C3%A0-rome>

⁶⁰ K. Zerouali, Director of Immigration and Border Surveillance. Ministry of the Interior, Rabat, Morocco. Telquel. September 27, 2018. https://telquel.ma/2018/09/27/khalid-zerouali-nos-moyens-sont-mobilises-contre-lemigration-nous-ne-pouvons-pas-faire-plus_1612072

policy discussions and public opinion, particularly in the context of increasing internal migration from sub-Saharan Africa⁶¹.

External Interests: Externally, Morocco's interests are shaped by its geopolitical and economic objectives. The country has strategically positioned itself as a key player in African migration politics, leveraging its role to strengthen ties with sub-Saharan African countries. This strategy is evident in Morocco's refusal to sign readmission agreements that would require it to accept third-country nationals who transited through its territory on their way to Europe. Such agreements could jeopardize Morocco's diplomatic relations with sub-Saharan nations, from which it seeks support on various political fronts, including the contentious Western Sahara issue. Therefore, Morocco's stance on return migration is also a reflection of its broader foreign policy goals and efforts to maintain favorable relations with its African neighbors⁶²

6.2.2. CAPACITIES OF RETURN MIGRATION GOVERNANCE⁶³

Morocco has developed considerable capacities to manage return migration through a combination of legal, institutional, and programmatic measures:

Legal Framework: The cornerstone of Morocco's return migration policy is its robust legal framework, including Law 02-03 and Law 27-14. These laws provide the legal foundation for managing the entry, stay, and return of migrants, including provisions for combating human trafficking and ensuring the protection of returnees' rights. This legal framework ensures that returns are conducted in compliance with international standards, which is crucial for maintaining Morocco's international reputation⁶⁴.

Support Programs: the AVRR, as the most important support program, provides critical support for returnees. These programs offer a range of services, including administrative assistance, financial aid, and logistical support, to ensure safe and dignified returns. Additionally, reintegration support, such as vocational training and small business grants, helps returnees rebuild their lives and contributes to reducing the likelihood of re-migration. According to IOM, these support mechanisms are essential for the sustainable reintegration of returnees into their home communities. They are carried out with "respect for the rights of migrants" and in connection with "freely expressed their will"⁶⁵.

6.3. SITUATION AND PERSPECTIVES OF MIGRANTS

6.3.1. Life conditions:

One of the migrants we met - expressing the opinion of his companions – said, “We are lions, used to the forest. We live among Moroccan and in the forest and we are prepared for any eventuality”.

⁶¹ See M. Lahlou, “EU-Africa Partnership on Migration and Mobility in Light of COVID-19: Perspectives from North Africa”. February 4, 2021. <https://www.iai.it/en/pubblicazioni/eu-africa-partnership-migration-and-mobility-light-covid-19-perspectives-north-africa>

⁶² According to former officials of the Moroccan Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Migration Affairs our team interviewed about this issue.

⁶³Idem.

⁶⁴At the end of this report, a diagram representing the main Actors involved in return policy from Morocco and a brief history of Moroccan migration Policies/approach

⁶⁵AMI-International Migration Organization Team interview, Rabat.

Very few migrants are aware of the Moroccan legislation in force on the migration issue, or the components of the National Immigration and Asylum Strategy.

Very few migrants are members of migrant associations, for several reasons, verifiable for many years: 1/the precariousness of their living and housing conditions; 2/ their high mobility between cities/regions of Morocco; 3/ the departure of many of them every year, to Europe, or the return of some of them to their country of origin; 4/ and finally, the fear of the Moroccan authorities.

Life between migrants is thus more organized between national communities or, particularly in the case of Nigerians, between communities of origin in their respective countries.

6.3.2. Main problems faced by the migrants living in Morocco:

Migrants living in Morocco encounter numerous challenges that affect their daily lives and overall well-being. These difficulties are rooted in precarious living conditions, limited access to basic services, and vulnerability to social and institutional pressures. The main issues they face include:

- Living in unsanitary conditions, especially concerning water and toilet issues;
- Problems occur in cases of significant "concentration" of migrants in certain streets and certain neighbourhoods;
- Deplorable living conditions include financial resources, access to food, or certain public services, such as healthcare.
- Submission to the forces of order. They can act, without notice, with great violence in certain situations of conflict with the Moroccan inhabitants, or in the event of political agreements with the Europeans (Spanish and French, in particular).

One fact seems obvious: the forced displacement of migrants from the border areas (with Spain) in the north of Morocco aims to keep migrants, potentially on their way, away from Europe as much as possible. More clearly, the approach of the Moroccan security forces is that there are as few "irregular" migrants as possible in the cities (and, especially, the city centres) of Tangier, Tetuan, or Rabat. As a result of such an approach, forced displacements, from city to city, are frequent.

- Existence among migrants – for their survival – of numerous trafficking, including drug trafficking.
- Prevalence of begging and prostitution, which is also the case, in poor neighbourhoods of cities in Morocco, of Moroccans in precarious situations.
- Many migrants live in cemeteries, near bus stations or train stations...
- Prevalence of small jobs: local shops, sewing, ethnic fast food, services (hairdressing, repairs of all equipment, homework, gardening, etc.).

6.3.3. Perspectives of migrants

According to the migrants we met, their goal is to leave, to leave this country (Morocco), and go to Europe. "We have no desire to stay in Morocco. But, if we don't manage to leave, we will return to our country. But, for that, the support of IOM is highly needed".

At this level, for the IOM, "there were several cumulative reasons for the "beneficiaries' decision" (candidates for return) to seek IOM's assistance to benefit from the AVRR program. Indeed, 61% of the migrants surveyed said that they had returned due to lack of financial

resources, preventing them from maintaining a sufficient level of subsistence in Morocco, while 15% said they had chosen to return after not being able to continue their migratory journey to their destination country (Europe). This situation explains the pressing and urgent needs expressed during the preparation of the return, particularly in terms of medical and food assistance and accommodation”⁶⁶.

In 97% of cases, the decision of the beneficiaries to return to their countries of origin was taken fairly quickly after arrival in Morocco (less than two years after arrival in Morocco) because of their vulnerable situation. IOM has established an intervention framework for migrants in particularly vulnerable situations (unaccompanied or separated children, migrants with health needs, potential victims of human trafficking) that allows for the identification of risks related to these vulnerabilities and the adaptation of responses to better ensure the support and protection of these categories of migrants throughout the voluntary return process. In 2022, the number of returns of unaccompanied or separated children doubled thanks to the strengthening of collaboration with the diplomatic representations of the countries of origin in the procedure of “determining the best interests of the child”.

Concerning the possibilities of reintegration of Nigerians returned to their home country, with the support of the IOM, it seems obvious to us that, despite their small number, this reintegration will be difficult. Thus, except for migrants who will have acquired some professional experience or made savings during their stay in Morocco - and who could take advantage of it to find a job or create their income-generating activity - it will be difficult for the others to reintegrate with dignity into their society. This is for the simple reason that the reasons which were at the origin of their migration still prevail in their country.

CONCLUSION

As indicated above, in 2024, Nigerians accounted for 3.4% of all migrants living in Morocco, representing approximately 5,000 individuals out of a total of 148,152.

When focusing on Nigerian returnees—who are the primary target of our research—they made up less than 7% (6.6%) of all returnees from Morocco in 2023. Specifically, 134 out of 2,007 Nigerian migrants voluntarily returned home that year. Additionally, Nigerian returnees represented 2.6% of the total Nigerian migrant population in Morocco (134 out of approximately 5,000).

These figures indicate that the return of Nigerian migrants from Morocco to Nigeria is not a significant issue for either Moroccan or Nigerian authorities. Given this data, the necessity of a readmission agreement between the two countries may be questionable.

From the perspective of the migrants we interviewed, their primary goal is to leave Morocco and reach Europe. One migrant stated: *“We have no desire to stay in Morocco. But if we don't manage to leave, we will return to our country. However, for that, the support of the IOM is highly needed.”*

At this level, the IOM has identified multiple cumulative reasons for migrants' decisions to seek assistance through the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) program. According to the IOM, 61% of surveyed migrants cited a lack of financial resources as their

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primary reason for returning, as they were unable to maintain a sufficient standard of living in Morocco. Additionally, 15% decided to return after failing to continue their journey to their intended destination, Europe. This situation explains the urgent needs expressed during the preparation for return, particularly in terms of medical and food assistance, as well as accommodation.

In 97% of cases, migrants decided to return to their home country relatively quickly—within less than two years of arriving in Morocco—due to their vulnerable situation. The IOM has established an intervention framework for particularly vulnerable migrants, including unaccompanied or separated children, individuals with health concerns, and potential victims of human trafficking. This framework allows for the identification of risks associated with these vulnerabilities and the adaptation of responses to better support and protect these groups throughout the voluntary return process.

In 2022, the number of returns of unaccompanied or separated children doubled, thanks to strengthened collaboration with the diplomatic representations of migrants' countries of origin in the process of *determining the best interests of the child*.

Regarding the reintegration of Nigerian returnees in their home country with IOM support, it is evident that, despite their small numbers, reintegration remains challenging. Unless migrants have acquired professional experience or saved money during their stay in Morocco—enabling them to find employment or start income-generating activities—many will struggle to reintegrate into society with dignity. This is primarily because the same factors that initially drove their migration persist in Nigeria.

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- University of Nigeria (Nigeria)
- Bilim Organization for Research and Social Studies (Afghanistan)
- Uniwersytet Warszawski (Poland)
- Migration Matters EV (Germany)
- University of Sousse (Tunisia)
- SPIA UG (Germany)
- University of Glasgow (UK, Associated Partner)

Annex: Main Actors involved in return policy from Morocco

Below are the main institutions supporting the return of irregular immigrants to their country of origin:

- **National Institutions :**
 - The Ministry of Interior
 - The Ministry of Foreign Affairs, African Cooperation, and Moroccans Residing Abroad
 - Local/territorial authorities
- **International Organisations:**
 - International Organization for Migration (IOM)
 - European Union (EU)
 - United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)
 - Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ)
- **Main diplomatic representations of countries of origin**

Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Côte d'Ivoire, Guinea Conakry, Mali, Democratic Republic of Congo, Senegal, Togo.

- **Civil society, NGOs, and specialists in legal, medical or research fields**
 - Orient-Occident Foundation;
 - Association for the Fight against AIDS (ALCS);
 - Tissaghness Association for Culture and Development (ASTICUDE);
 - Bayti Association;
 - Morocco Medico-Socio-Solidarity (MS2);
 - Moroccan Family Planning Association (AMPF);
 - Progettomondo.
- **Several other initiatives strengthen the AVRRE program. These include, among others :**
 - COMPASS - Cooperation on Migration and Partnerships to Achieve Sustainable Solutions (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Netherlands)
 - The EU – IOM Joint Initiative for Migrant Protection and Reintegration in North Africa
 - FORAS - Enhancing reintegration opportunities from Morocco (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Germany)
 - ORION - Operationalises an integrated approach to reintegration
 - Assistance and protection of unaccompanied and separated children
 - RDPP NA - Development Pillar to Support the Regional Development and Protection Program in North Africa
 - Fostering Health and Protection to Vulnerable Migrants Transiting through Morocco, Tunisia, Egypt, Libya, Yemen, and Sudan.
- **Funders:**
 - Kingdom of the Netherlands
 - Kingdom of Spain
 - Kingdom of Norway
 - United Kingdom
 - Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC)
 - European Union (Emergency Trust Fund for Africa)⁶⁷.

Regarding the last contributor/funder, the EU, it has allocated approximately €1.5 billion to overall bilateral cooperation with Morocco between 2014 and 2020, including contributions through the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF). Additionally, between 2021 and 2022, the EU allocated €631 million under the Neighbourhood, Development, and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI – Global Europe). Morocco also receives EU funding for migration under other financing instruments, such as the Asylum, Migration, and Integration Fund (AMIF), which supported 2,908 voluntary returns to countries of origin.

⁶⁷ The EU has devoted around €1.5 billion to overall bilateral cooperation with Morocco between 2014 and 2020, including the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF). The EU also allocated €631 million between 2021 and 2022 under the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI – Global Europe). The country is also a recipient of EU funding for migration under other financing instruments, i.e. the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF). It supported 2,908 voluntary returns to the countries of origin.

https://trust-fund-for-africa.europa.eu/document/download/6690bcbf-3bec-40e1-b80e-f57a724cdf09_en?filename=EU_support_migration_morocco_Kostas.pdf

Building on the work of the EUTF, €150 million has been allocated in 2022 for a four-year Budget Support program. The primary objective of this program is to strengthen EU-Morocco cooperation and dialogue on migration while contributing to the objectives of Morocco's National Immigration and Asylum Strategy (SNIA).

Morocco also benefits from regional support under the following initiatives for North Africa:

€10 million for a regional action to prevent irregular migration and combat migrant smuggling.

€5 million for a regional action to support labor migration governance and labor mobility.

€60 million for a regional action to enhance protection and promote return, readmission, and sustainable reintegration.

€18 million for a regional action to support legal migration, mobility, and skills partnerships.